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Preparation of a Multicultural Teacher at a University

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the urgent problem of modern education and upbringing of a multicultural teacher. The purpose of this article is to identify the ways and mechanisms of preparing a multicultural teacher in a university environment. The article discusses issues related to the understanding of multiculturalism, multiculturalism, means and mechanisms of its implementation in a multipolar educational environment.

Particular problems arise when preparing a teacher for activities in a multi-ethnic and multicultural environment. Obviously, appropriate adjustments should be made to teacher education programs. We are talking about changes in theoretical training (knowledge of the principles, specifics, tasks of multicultural education), as well as the mastery of certain methods of such education. In multi-ethnic educational institutions, teachers who speak at least two languages - Russian and the language of one or another minority should work.

Unfortunately, in modern pedagogy there are no clearly oriented goals of multicultural education, the ways to achieve which and the results obtained could be unambiguously and objectively diagnosed. The wider and more significant the goals of multicultural education, the more difficult they are applicable in practice. The target setting when creating educational, multicultural technologies will take the form of the expected result only when they are specific, personality-oriented and reflect the patterns of the educational process to the maximum.

According to the rules, multicultural education strategy is built is a means of realizing respect for the pupil, while they are implemented in special forms that determine the conditions that ensure the effectiveness of the technology requirements. The higher the exactingness to a person, the more respect for him or her.

The success of multicultural education depends on the nature of the student's inclusion in various activities, as well as on the form, method, and means of instruction.

The effectiveness of the implementation of multicultural, educational technologies will largely depend on the pedagogical conditions in which they are implemented. Such pedagogical conditions include - erudition, multiculturalism, originality of the personality of the teacher, his ethical culture, interests, hobbies, etc.; tolerant attitude towards pupils, expressed in pedagogical tact, optimism; deep knowledge of the laws of the multicultural educational process and child psychology, knowledge of diagnostic methods, etc.

Today's teacher should be aimed at the adoption of multiculturalism and humanization of the entire educational process, at creating a system of interaction with students in any multicultural environment. It is also necessary to take into account the characteristics of the student's personality, ethnicity, mentality, national culture, psychological, gender and other characteristics of the student.

This article will be interesting to teachers of universities and educational institutions, specialists in the field of multicultural education.

Keywords: multicultural education, the concept of multicultural education, methods, forms of multicultural education, multicultural teacher.

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Introduction

The formation of ethnic identity of young people is very important in modern conditions of tension and open hatred in different countries of the world. Therefore, today teachers and parents need a meaningful approach to the problem of multiculturalism. This is an important part of the culture of interethnic relations in a multi-ethnic society, its differentiation taking into account different national and age groups of the region's population, the level of formation of national consciousness of the culture of interethnic and interpersonal relations.

The concept of development of multicultural education in the Russian Federation is based on the need to educate children in the spirit of respect for cultural values and differences of different peoples of the country and the world (Government of the Russian Federation, n.d.). The state is required to create special conditions for the implementation of multicultural pedagogy in public relations and the educational environment, starting with the family, kindergarten, school, and university (Makaev & Suprunova, 1994).

The relevance of the research is due to the result of multicultural education, which reflects qualitative changes in the personal and activity characteristics of the student, is multicultural education (or multiculturalism), that is, the formation of socio-cultural (multicultural) competence. Such competence can be characterized as a set of national (folk) knowledge and skills, the ability to apply them adequately in life, the formation of national value orientations and positive attitudes that ensure successful self-realization of the individual and the possibility of active social interaction (Makaev & Suprunova, 1994).

The ideas of multiculturalism have deep historical roots. Thoughts about the need for personal development in a multicultural environment have been developed in philosophical and pedagogical works for many generations. Therefore, it can be concluded that multiculturalism in education and upbringing is the integration of a person into culture, conflict-free identity in a multicultural society.

Russia, being a multicultural society, needs a worldview aimed at integrating cultures and people with the purpose of their further rapprochement and spiritual enrichment. The main provisions of multicultural education are reflected in the concept of development of multicultural education in the Russian Federation Confederations (Government of the Russian Federation, n.d.).

Changes in upbringing and education towards multiculturalism have been observed in the last 50 years. Although in the early twentieth century the answer to anti-vilification school and society was assimilation of students from national minorities, but since the second half of the last century foregrounds the problem of interethnic tolerance and understanding.

In the 60s of the twentieth century, educational requirements were formulated based on the recognition of the value and consideration of cultural diversity.

Since the 70s of the twentieth century, special programs for multicultural education of immigrants, indigenous ethnic and racial minorities have been developed.

Modern multicultural programs can stimulate interest in new knowledge and simultaneously represent different views and opinions about the multicultural world surrounding the individual, which is reflected in the levels of multicultural upbringing of the individual.

In the world of pedagogical science, the criteria for the effectiveness of multicultural education are highlighted. Simmons et al. (2010) offers the following levels, acquired as a result of the formation of multicultural education (competence):

Levels of multicultural education

Level 1. Awareness and understanding	Level 2. Assessment and consent	Level 3. Beliefs protection
Awareness of your own ethnic group, race, etc.	The promotion of social justice.	Designing, implementing and evaluating multicultural experiences.
Understanding social inequality.	Promoting the development of feelings of unity.	Realistic and critical attitude to social activities.
Awareness of the ways in which social institutions, including schools, perpetuate discrimination and prejudice.	Acceptance of cultural pluralism, promotion of development a positive "I" concept.	Actions for positive social change. Readiness to solve racial and social problems.
Acquisition of knowledge about other cultural groups, their contribution to society, history, ideals, beliefs. Accumulation of relevant experience in school.	Liberation from stereotypes. Acquisition of multicultural education. Intergroup intercultural training.	The use of personal experience in the analysis of cultural discrimination. Active involvement in the democratic solution of socio-cultural problems.

Methods for identifying the results and effectiveness of multicultural education are constantly improving. Multi-stage diagnostics is proposed: first stage — surveys, questionnaires, ratings, observations, etc.; the second is testing. playing problem situations and so on; the third — self-assessment, analysis of activities; the fourth — selection of indicators-indicators of individual activity in a multinational society.

The increased concentration of representatives of various ethnic groups in the social environment, in some cases, is accompanied by the creation of special psychological and pedagogical conditions for them in institutions (schools) working under special programs.

Therefore, the teacher that an educational institution needs today should be aimed at accepting multiculturalism and humanizing the entire educational process, at creating a system of interaction with students in any multicultural environment, it is also necessary to take into account the characteristics of their personality, ethnicity, mentality, national culture, psychological, gender and other characteristics of the student.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of our research is to identify the psychological and pedagogical conditions for successful functioning in the multicultural space of the teacher. To do this, the teacher needs to achieve a certain level of professional development, characterized by the presence of a system of professionally important qualities that cover all aspects of his or her own personality, the significance of which is mentioned in the works of Slastenin and Baranov (1976) and Pavlova (2016).

Literature review

Analysis of the development of pedagogical theory and practice shows that at all stages of the development of a multiethnic society the problems of introducing people to national values in connection with universal and nurturing the culture of interethnic relations of the younger generation occupied a significant place in the works of teachers: Gessen (1995), Ushinsky (1988). The work of Volkov (1999) affects problems of features of the content of education, which is determined by the multicultural social environment. The ideas of implementing ethnic traditions in education were developed in the research of Dmitriev (1999), and others. He expresses the opinion that it is necessary to introduce solutions to the spectrum of problems.

Issues related to a multicultural approach to education have been discussed at many International, National, and Regional scientific and practical conferences. Multicultural education as a tool for integrating national minorities into the dominant cultural environment was studied by Dmitriev (1999); the concept of multicultural interaction in foreign pedagogy was studied by Naushabayeva (1993); the work of Menskaya (1993) is devoted to the implementation of the multicultural approach in the content of the educational process. Issues of multicultural education are reflected in the dissertation research of Tkach (2002). These works address the problems of educational content, which are determined by the multicultural social environment. Thoughts are expressed about the need for introduction to the spectrum problems of general education of new components caused by multiculturalism of students.

Analysis of the content of the Law of the Russian Federation "on education" shows that the study of any discipline at each stage of education, extracurricular work should contribute to the education, formation and development of students' national identity and national consciousness, necessary for their further self-realization in modern society (Government of the Russian Federation, 2012).

The success of multicultural education in the educational process depends on many factors: the content of the educational material, the organization of intellectual labor, the relationship between all components of educational activities, the nature of teaching methods. The main role in this belongs to the methods of training and education designed to implement the overall content of education.

In modern pedagogy, special attention is paid to the study of the problem of multicultural education. Professional training of teachers is presented in the work of Yankina (2005). Problems of teaching schoolchildren in the system of dialogue of

cultures are considered in the work of Bibler (1992). The basics of intercultural interaction in the preparation of future teachers are considered by Galskova (2008). Theoretical aspects of interaction pedagogy in the modern educational process are considered by Rodionova (1989). But in these studies, the teacher's readiness for professional activity in a multicultural team was not specifically studied.

The problems of improving teacher-student interaction in a multicultural educational space prove the importance of introducing a new methodological approach to teacher training. In this regard, the pedagogical conditions for preparing a teacher for his professional activity in a multicultural group of students are reconsidered, and the definition of effective forms of organizing the educational process is clarified.

The lack of systematic professional training of future teachers and the teaching staff of educational institutions in this area is the reason for the growth of manifestations of ethnophobia and everyday nationalism in our country.

Methodology

In the course of the experimental study, we conducted a survey of 68 teachers from three schools in the city of Ulan-Ude, according to questionnaires prepared by teachers of the Buryat State University of the Pedagogical Institute in advance. The sample of respondents was carried out according to their wishes, while the following analysis tools were used: observation, work with a survey group of students to conduct an experiment, a survey, collection and interpretation of the data, statistical conclusions. Along with this, a survey group of students and teachers tried to create favorable psychological and pedagogical conditions during the study: an adequate psychological attitude towards a multicultural perception of the school environment, positive emotional interaction between participants in a multicultural exchange, etc.

In our further study, various forms of multicultural education were actively used: trainings, quests, conferences, special courses in educational institutions, which helped to increase the multicultural level of students and teachers. The result of the survey was that almost every participant expressed a desire to get additional knowledge on the problem of multicultural education.

Results

Teacher surveys conducted by an experimental group of students of the Pedagogical Institute of the Buryat State University showed that 45% of respondents see the need for timely preparation of students to avoid national conflicts, 67% of respondents say that the Republic of Buryatia is prepared to receive immigrants, 38% believe our society is not ready to accept immigrants. The question about the means of effective assistance in the adaptation of immigrant students caused difficulties for the respondents. And to the question whether teachers are able to prepare their pupils for intercultural interaction, only 37% answered positively. Teachers explain this by the fact that the training process does not aim them at solving this problem. When being asked what multicultural knowledge is not enough for a modern teacher, 34% of respondents believe that they lack knowledge on the ethno-pedagogical characteristics of representatives of different peoples living in Russia, 58% - knowledge on ethnopsychology, and 56% would like to get acquainted with the basics of migration law (Pavlova, 2012).

School as an environment of multicultural education in the XXI century it is developed under the following conditions that can be included in the system of professional development of teachers, which implies their assimilation of a specially designed knowledge module in areas of theory and practice of multicultural education:

- methodological apparatus of multicultural education: the relationship of universal, international and national started in the concept of "multicultural education»;
- culture as a basic concept of multicultural education; functions of culture, world, universal, national, personal culture;
- multicultural education as a cultural phenomenon; the mechanism of multiculturalism-polylogue and dialogue of cultures; multilingual and bilingual personality;
- global processes in the development of multicultural education;
- tasks of multicultural education, goals, functions (humanistic-orientation, cultural, educational, communicative, adaptive);
- a model for implementing multicultural education based on leading pedagogical paradigms: personality-oriented, its criteria;
- culturological approach as an objective relationship between a person and culture, value system;
- synergetic approach as a pedagogical system of self-actualization of the individual in multicultural education;
- development of folk education and ethnopedagogics in multicultural education; subject, tasks, means, factors of development-folk education, stereotypes and autostereotypes in ethnopedagogics, the problem of the ratio of multicultural education and ethnopedagogics; - ethnopedagogical dialogue;
- pedagogical culture of a school teacher in a multicultural educational space;
- conceptual ideas for the development of multicultural education in Russia school;
- formation of the humanitarian environment;
- specific features of multicultural education: a combination of national (language, history, art, folklore, traditions national pedagogy) and national categories;
- dynamic process of pedagogical interaction in multicultural education; specifics of the content of multicultural education education (globalism, planetary worldview, Humanities personal culture);
- the essence of the principles of multicultural education (personality-oriented, cultural approach, regionalization of education);

- integration of pedagogical interaction based on a comprehensive approach, taking into account ethnic, individual, differentiated approaches;
- goal setting of the school for the implementation of multicultural education: the goals of multicultural education in the school are defined social, migration, and historical conditions of life;
- development of multicultural education in the context of the school's humanitarian culture;
- the content of multicultural education in schools is determined in particular by the leading cultural traditions and ideas tolerance, religious tolerance, national and universal values, preparing students for life in a multicultural society taking into account the content of multicultural education unity of regional and global factors (global capital tasks of the process of multicultural education);
- organization of multicultural education in schools: a person-oriented approach, dialogue and polylogue;
- orientation to the zone of nearest development of humanitarian culture;
- self-actualization, self-education and self-expression of the individual as a factor in the formation of multiculturalism of the student in school at the crossroads of cultures ("at the crossroads of cultures" — Harvard multicultural education course»);
- ways to implement multicultural education in schools: assimilation of scientific and educational, philosophical, ethnological information;
- analysis of socio-cultural migration phenomena and multicultural differences;
- association and identification of students to the values of multiculturalism, to a particular culture;
- formation of cognitive interest in the problems of multicultural society;
- education of students through the educational process and additional education of subcultural orientation, mastering cultural decision-making mechanism, ability development to self-realization, the potential of the student in the areas of youth cultures and subcultures in particular.

Training teachers for professional activities in a multicultural group of students will allow them to develop their professional competence, if conditions are implemented that provide for the special organization of additional education and self-education of teachers based on an understanding of the essence multicultural group of students; if the goals, content and methods of special training of teachers will meet the needs of a multicultural group of students in taking into account the characteristics and interests of national groups, in optimizing the processes of cultural adaptation, in preventing and resolving inter-ethnic conflicts, as well as the self-realization of each individual preserving ethnic identity.

The ideal multicultural teacher should demonstrate such qualities as: the ability to simultaneously teach and educate, a solid theoretical pedagogical education, high culture and awareness of the values of education, freedom and

responsibility, a sense of belonging to the intellectual elite, high moral qualities, love your students, regardless of their ethnic, cultural, or religious affiliation. Personal the qualities of a multicultural teacher should be in harmony with professional knowledge and skills.

Discussions

In the course of conversations with students, future teachers, it turned out that they feel the need to conduct special seminars on the problems of pedagogical and interethnic communication in a multicultural environment, the choice of pedagogical means of influencing modern students, the creation and resolution of special situations that arise when working in a multicultural team, that is, they need specially developed teaching aids to help overcome the above difficulties.

More than half of the students surveyed are of the opinion that in connection with the expected demographic changes and migration processes in the Republic of Buryatia, the regional authorities should make adjustments to the system of retraining of national teaching staff.

Conclusion

We believe that the creation of favorable psychological and pedagogical conditions (a psychological attitude to multicultural perception in the school environment, positive emotional interaction of participants in multicultural exchange, etc.) and the active use of various forms of multicultural education: trainings, quests, conferences, special courses in educational institutions, the opening of national cultural centers, etc. will increase the multicultural level of teachers in general.

We believe that within the framework of this work, the effectiveness of the identified psychological and pedagogical conditions for successful functioning in the multicultural space of the teacher has been experimentally proved.

The results of our research can be used by teachers in working with a multi-ethnic composition of students, improve the multicultural interaction of children and adults. Some of the conclusions of our research were presented in the author's educational manual "Multicultural education" (Pavlova, 2016a; Pavlova, 2016b).

Thus, positive social life and pluralistic views of the teaching staff, a favorable social multicultural environment, as well as pedagogical practice in national classes, monitoring and analysis of the work of teachers in a multicultural group of students, research on the problems of multicultural educational space are important conditions for preparing a multicultural teacher for professional activity in a diverse national team of students (Yagodina, 2005).

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